

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL PLATFORMS IN SOCIO-POLITICAL PROCESSES

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One of the most promising approaches to improving society is the use of digital technologies that provide participatory governance. Such technologies are already enabling individuals and communities to have a direct say in decisions that affect them, resulting in more flexible, responsive, trustworthy

Participatory budgeting¹, a participatory process in the allocation of resources and control of public expenditures, has emerged as a democratic innovation² and successful participatory tool to involve citizens directly in the political decision-making process.

Participatory budgeting has been used in many cities around the world. Since the emergence of participatory budgeting in the 1990s, this process has helped to counter the problems of political patronage and social exclusion. It also increases political legitimacy by making the budget process transparent, open and public. It can also be a good additional measure for forms of representation, as participatory budgeting can better meet the diverse needs of underrepresented minority groups.

In recent years, the increasing use of digital technologies and platforms has allowed cities to directly involve more citizens in the collective decision-making process. The digitization of Participatory Budgeting, especially in parts of Europe and North America, provides great opportunities for various stakeholders to effectively participate in large-scale political decision-making

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¹ Participatory budgeting (PB) is a form of citizen involvement in which ordinary people decide how to allocate part of the municipal or state budget through a democratic discussion and decision-making process. Participatory budgeting allows citizens or residents to identify, discuss and prioritize public spending projects and empowers them to make real decisions about how money is spent.

² Ryan M. Why Citizen Participation Succeeds Or Fails : A Comparative Analysis of Participatory Budgeting (first ed.), Bristol University Press, Bristol (2021)

³ Wampler B., McNulty S., Touchton M. Participatory Budgeting in Global Perspective

decade has seen the rapid growth of open-source citizen participation platforms such as Decidim⁴ and Consul^{5,6} which support large-scale "crowdfunding".

Citizen participation programs can be a useful tool to identify problems and direct resources to the most needy groups and regions. New digital tools are increasingly being used to support citizen participation, thereby strengthening democracy, and to support cities and institutions in meeting the demands of accountability and transparency.

Citizen participation through Digital platforms has played an important role in the development of cooperation. The proliferation of digital platforms such as Decidim and Consul has also made it easier to share this type of information and resources, allowing cities to solve their complex problems together. By using digital participatory budgeting, cities not only empower their citizens to actively participate in the budget process, but also build a global network of interconnected urban communities.

Electronic IDs - Discussions about voting in digital societies have recently revolved around electronic IDs (e-IDs) and the potential to avoid paper ballots. However, there are many concerns that democratic "disruption" is possible, meaning that election results may be biased.

In addition, there is intense debate about how electronic IDs will work, what biometric features they will use, and who should be responsible for the appropriate platform(s) and data management. That is, different voting rules can be used to determine the result of the vote, and this can make a significant difference.

Voting systems - Voting is aimed at solving problems of collective decisions ("social choice") when there are different opinions, interests and needs. It is essential in decision making, consensus building and conflict resolution in various political and international contexts. In particular, voting methods and their legitimacy are important for finding effective solutions among different interest groups, and they are widely supported.

Voters are required to properly express their wishes by voting. "Access Method" specifies the method to do this. The "aggregation method" then turns the votes into a collective decision.

The more diverse or complex the community, the more important this can be. **Square voting**⁷ aims to prevent such unwanted outcomes and has gained some

⁴ Decidim is a digital platform for citizen participation

⁵ <https://consuldemocracy.org/>

⁶ The most comprehensive citizen participation tool for open, transparent and democratic government

traction for collective decision-making and blockchain governance. It differs from traditional voting methods by allowing voters to express the intensity of their preferences using voting credits. By making it "expensive" to choose only one option, Quadratic Voting helps protect minority interests and encourages diversity. Diversity, in turn, strengthens team spirit; Therefore, voting innovations that provide different results deserve serious attention.

Smart Agora⁸ is a "living-lab" experience platform for team members using smartphones. It collects geo-located sensor, survey and polling data, verifies what users have witnessed, and examines conditions for more informed and evidence-based decision-making. Smart Agora turns every part of the city into a digital voting center, creating conditions for more informed citizens to make decisions. For example, in a budgeting debate, changes are made to the project after the voter has numerically proven that they are sufficiently informed about

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DIAS is a real-time decentralized data analysis service for large-scale network users. DIAS users share enhanced summaries of personal and local information with each other. This allows each of them to aggregate votes, to calculate locally, such as the average importance of proposals in different communities or the highest scores. With information sharing, flexibility, and self-determination of information in updating accounts, DIAS supports inclusion, privacy, autonomy, participation, decision quality, trust, and legitimacy, as shown in Figure 1.

EPOS is a collective learning algorithm for discrete choice multi-objective optimization problems in the context of decentralized multi-agent systems.

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⁷ **Square voting** is a collective decision-making procedure in which people allocate votes to represent their degree of preference, rather than the direction of their preferences. K.o. giving seeks to resolve the issues of Condorcet's paradox and majority rule. Square voting allows users to "pay" for additional votes on a given issue, allowing them to express their support for a given issue more strongly, resulting in voting results based solely on the user's preferences. matches the results with the highest willingness to pay, not the rgan result. Payment for votes can be made with artificial or real currencies (for example, with tokens distributed equally among voting members or with real money

⁸ Smart Agora envisions a cyber-physical digital agora in Smart Cities, a public discourse space where citizens actively participate in collective decision-making and public issues.

⁹ Proof of witness presence: blockchain consensus for augmented democracy in smart cities J. Parallel Distrib. Comput., 145 (2020), pp. 160-175

¹⁰ Blockchain is a decentralized distributed digital system consisting of a chain of blocks containing transaction data that can be shared across the network among networked participants in an encrypted form.

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EPOS is applied to a wide range of scheduling and resource allocation problems, including balancing and matching objectives: consumer energy management, electric vehicle charging control, load balancing of bicycle sharing stations, traffic rerouting, edge-to-cloud load balancing and more. Through information self-determination, coordination, informed decisions, resilience, and decentralized computing, EPOS captures the large spectrum of values defined in Figure 1.

These examples illustrate the growing complexity and interdisciplinary challenge of integrating engineering values into the support of digital platforms for democratic innovations. Further work is required to extend promising governance and engagement platforms such as Decidim with value-sensitive digital support.

To sum up, the world is going through a digital revolution. Rapid technological advances are changing the way we live, work and communicate. The Internet, social media, cloud computing, and mobile technology are just a few of the innovations that are changing our society. This digital revolution will also have a significant impact on how we manage our societies. Figure 1 summarizes the potential benefits and risks of these innovations for democracy. In general, we need a paradigm shift.

	Existing	Possible
Positive	Easy access to information Ease to share opinions	Collective intelligence Increased representativity
Negative	Misinformation Hate speech	Manipulation Centralized power Privacy breach

Figure 1

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We have explained how digital tools can help democratically renew society by providing platforms for people to engage in dialogue and debate, facilitate the exchange of information and ideas, empower individuals to act, and embrace technology. They also help to increase the transparency and accountability of the government and the positive ease the negative effects of digital tools in democratic processes. However, should not be paid to remember that digital tools are not a magic wand. They should be used as opportunities and not as a threat. Other measures such as education, awareness raising, inclusiveness, spatial equity and democracy promotion.

While there are many challenges that need to be addressed, such as ensuring that all voices are heard and that everyone has access to digital tools, the potential of digital technologies to democratize society is huge.

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